

Yellow Flavonols of *Decaschistia crotonifolia*

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THE genus *Decaschistia* belongs to the family *Malvaceae* and only three of its species occur in South India¹ viz., *Decaschistia crotonifolia*, *D. rufa* and *D. triloba*. None of these species has been subjected to chemical investigation. The yellow flowers of *D. crotonifolia* has been collected from Tirumala Hills for the present investigation.

The flowers were first defatted by extraction with light petroleum and benzene, and then subjected to acetone extraction. The acetone extract when concentrated and set aside deposited a greenish yellow solid. Thin layer chromatographic examination of the solid showed it to be a mixture of three compounds. They were separated by chromatography over polyamide (Woelm) column, using ethanol-water (1:1 v/v) as eluent, to obtain three crystalline compounds A, B and C.

Compound A crystallised from aqueous ethanol as green leaflets melting at 232-4°. It was analysed for $C_{21}H_{20}O_{13} \cdot H_2O$. It gave an olive-green ferric reaction, positive Molisch test and an orange red Shinoda test. The U. V. spectrum of the compound, λ_{max} 262 and 392 nm showed it to be a flavonol glycoside. On acid hydrolysis, it gave an aglycone, which was identified as gossypetin, by the formation of blue colour with sodium acetate², by positive gossypetone test³ and by spectral and chromatographic comparison with an authentic sample. The aqueous part on working up for sugar showed the presence of glucose. Thus compound A is a monoglucoside of gossypetin. In the U. V. spectrum, addition of sodium acetate⁴ did not cause bathochromic shift of the short wavelength band, thereby indicating that the glucose residue was present at the 7-position of gossypetin. The glycoside also gave a positive gossypetone test substantiating the presence of a 5,8-quinol system. The NMR spectrum* of its acetate taken in $CdCl_2$, showed signals due to five phenolic acetyls at 7.58 (3H), 7.64 (3H) and 7.68 (9H) and four alcoholic acetyls at 7.92, 7.94, 7.96 and 7.98. The A-ring proton at 6-position appeared as a singlet at 3.2. The B-ring protons formed an ABX pattern characteristic of 3',4'-oxygenated flavonoids⁵. The 2' proton showed up as a doublet at 2.28 (J=2.5 Hz) while 5' and 6' protons appeared as a doublet at 2.65 (J=8.5 Hz) and as a quartet at 2.35 (J=2.5 and 8.5 Hz) respectively. Thus compound A is identified as gossypetrin.

Compound B crystallised as yellow needle-shaped clusters with melting point 225-6°. Elemental analysis

gave the molecular formula $C_{21}H_{20}O_{12} \cdot H_2O$. It gave green ferric reaction, orange red Shinoda test and a positive Molisch test. Its U. V. spectrum showed maxima at 258 and 378 nm indicating the compound to be flavonol glycoside. U.V. spectral shifts with the diagnostic reagents, sodium methoxide, aluminium chloride and boric acid-sodium acetate showed the presence of free hydroxyls at 3,3',4' and 5-positions. But addition of sodium acetate did not cause any bathochromic shift of the short wave length band indicating that the sugar residue is linked to the 7-position. Acid hydrolysis of the compound gave an aglycone, which was characterised as quercetin by chromatographic and spectral comparison with an authentic sample. Thus compound B is identified as quercimeritrin (Quercetin-7-o-glucoside) and the NMR spectrum of its acetate confirmed the structure.

Compound C crystallised as lemon-yellow needles from aqueous ethanol and melted at 235-7°. It was analysed for $C_{21}H_{20}O_{13} \cdot \frac{1}{2}H_2O$ and gave positive Molisch and Shinoda tests and a green ferric reaction. It did not answer gossypetone test. U.V. absorption maxima at 261 and 383 nm showed it to be a flavonol glycoside. With the help of diagnostic reagents the presence of free hydroxyls at 3,3',4',5 and 7-positions is established. On acid hydrolysis, it gave gossypetin and glucose. Negative gossypetone test required the glucose residue to be linked to the 8-position of gossypetone. Thus compound C is identified as gossypin and its structure is confirmed by the NMR spectrum. The NMR spectrum taken in $DMSO-d_6$ showed a one proton signal due to H-6 at 3.76. The remaining aromatic signals, doublets at 2.12 (J=2.5 Hz) and 3.06 (J=8.5 Hz) and a quartet at 2.18 (J=2.5 and 8.5 Hz) were assigned to H-2', H-5' and H-6' respectively. The sugar protons appeared in the region 4.5-6.9.

It is interesting to note the presence of gossypetrin and gossypin along with quercimeritrin in *Decaschistia crotonifolia*.

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* N.M.R. given in τ values.